

APPLICATION OF SMART TECHNOLOGIES FOR IMPROVEMENTS IN FACILITIES MANAGEMENT

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ABSTRACT

Sustainable maintenance of buildings and infrastructure is key to the economic development of any nation as a growing economy will need to provide adequate shelter for its workforce. Recent developments in building technologies have therefore placed a demand on methods of securing such facilities and systems of managing access. This paper looks into the utilization of smart technologies to secure and manage access in and out of building facilities. The design and development of a door access system include many different features, from as simple as a keypad to as complex as using smart cards and biometrics. The Dual Access Door System using an open-source Arduino MEGA is developed to enhance security and control access to an enclosed room which allows users to use either a PIN or a registered fingerprint to gain access. The inputs to the system are the fingerprint scanner and a numerical keypad. The outputs are a solenoid door lock, an LCD, and a buzzer. For the prototype developed, the system can register just four fingerprints. The details obtained by scanning fingerprints are clarified as the input, while instructions on what to do are displayed on the LCD. During implementation, the result of the test shows the system to be very effective and easy to use. The system is reliable and can lead to a reduction in the overall cost of facility management.

Keywords: Smart Technology, Door Access System, Fingerprint, Access Control Management

INTRODUCTION

Recent developments in building technologies that have led to rapid production of building facilities and infrastructure have placed a demand on methods of sustaining and maintaining these facilities (Adelakun et al., 2022). Before now, challenges in facilities management have placed a cap on the national sustainability of building infrastructure and facilities across the globe, thus limiting the economic growth between these nations. Research has shown a link between housing (facilities) and economic development, as highlighted by Terzi & Bolen (2008). Their paper further shows that investment and development in housing comprise 2–8% of the gross national product (GNP) and 10–30% of the gross fixed investment in developing countries like Nigeria. One of the major areas where remarkable improvements are needed in the facility management sector is the security and management of access control in and out of building facilities and infrastructure. People throughout the world have always been concerned about the security and safety of lives and assets, which has led to the utilisation of manual lock systems to protect buildings and facilities while employing humans to manage access control to record entry data. Nevertheless, there are still limitations that retard the sustainability of building facilities and management systems. Therefore, there is an urgent need for facility management improvements regarding security and access control. Here, the application of smart technology can be employed to improve facility management across the globe. ‘Smart’ technology refers to integrating computing and telecommunication technology into other technologies that did not previously have such capabilities (Abdelkarim et al., 2023; Adelakun, 2024; Dong et al., 2020). What makes a technology ‘smart’ is its ability to communicate and work with other networked technologies, and

through this ability to allow automated or adaptive functionality as well as remote accessibility or operation from anywhere. An area of application of smart technology in facility management is the incorporation of modern computing technologies like Arduino with facilities access control systems (Jia et al., 2019; Yaïci et al., 2021).

An Access Control system generally consists of secured gates, doors, or barriers that require identity authentication, such as RFID access cards, pin codes, facial recognition, fingerprints, or smartphones, to grant access to a building or specific area (Cie-group, n.d.). Some of these access control systems may be coupled with a manual method of documenting access by having a register where anyone who enters or leaves the facilities signs. However, these locks have proved to be inadequate because of advances in technology and the need for personalised lock systems. But by bringing modern computing technologies to our system of access control, we have ourselves today, a more robust access control system that can be pre-programmed based on the required need as it implements modern computing technologies to authenticate, secure, and document access in and out of facilities, providing diverse functions all at once. The technology of biometrics is now being used with door access systems in our world today. Biometrics can be defined as a practical means of identifying and authenticating an individual's unique physical and behavioural characteristics in a reliable and fast way. Biometric authentication refers to the identification of humans by their characteristics or traits (Palma & Montessoro, 2022). Common biometric methods include fingerprint, iris scan, face recognition, and palm vein. Biometrics are now used in door locks, such that their authentication method involves unique features of the human body, which may be a fingerprint, an iris pattern, etc. They use a scanner to store the biometric data of anyone authorized to unlock your door. Once the scanner determines that you are an authorised user, it grants access to unlock the door. These locks are meant to provide convenience since you don't have to keep track of a key, more than additional security (Kumar & Ryu, 2009).

However, our focus will be on the utilisation of fingerprints. The fingerprint is an old, time-tested biometric. Fingerprinting technology is one of the well-established technologies used in security and general-purpose identification (Memon et al., 2009). Today, it is used for a large variety of different applications, from identifying suspects at the scene of a crime and conducting background checks to authenticating payments and unlocking mobile devices. Generally, the features of fingerprint recognition systems include faster speed, lower costs, and more consistency compared to other types of biometric devices. Every person has a separate model of the fingerprint, which is made with ridges, that create whorls and loops that are unique to every person. Fingerprints are classified into five types: whorl, right loop, left loop, tented, and arch. (Moses et al., 2015). Fingerprint identification is a method of identification based on the different patterns of human fingers, which are unique to each person. It is the most popular way of acquiring details about any person and is the easiest and most convenient way of identifying them. The fingerprint identification method has the advantage of maintaining a person's fingerprint pattern throughout his or her life, making it an infallible method of human identification (Bose & Kabir, 2017). A fingerprint scanner is used to acquire the details of a person's fingerprint (Alsmirat et al., 2019). They come in various sizes and shapes but generally fall into two categories; area scan (or touch) scanners and swipe scanners (Memon et. al., 2009). The measure of the fingerprint image quality is in dots per inch (DPI). Based on the technology employed, fingerprint scanners that either scan or touch fall into one of the following major sensor types: optical, capacitive, thermal, or ultrasonic fingerprint scanners.

One of the many advantages presented by a fingerprint-based lock is the provision of improved security. The traditional lock and key-based systems have plenty of vulnerabilities. The major one

among them is the fact that the key can be easily duplicated. This would result in unpleasant surprises at any point in time. With fingerprints being unique, it is next to impossible for someone to break into your premises with the use of a biometric lock. The risk of misplacing the key is also eliminated since the key needed for authenticating access is always with the user's finger. A fingerprint-based system provides an easy-to-use access system, as all a user needs to do is press their finger against the scanner (Esekhaigbe & Okoduwa, 2022). There is no need for training on how to use the system, making the process quite convenient and quick. Fingerprint-based door access systems have proven to be cost-effective when compared to other forms of biometric access systems. Hence, the security provided by a fingerprint is high. With a key-based system, burglars can break or pick the lock; hence, it is not fail-proof. Card-based systems can be hacked into, and if misplaced or stolen, the costs of replacing them run very high. Fingerprint-based systems are complicated, if not impossible, to hack into. Since each person has a unique implementation, which is the only criterion required to get access, the security provided is quite reassuring.

METHODOLOGY

The design and construction of this smart door access system involve two parts, which are software and hardware parts. The software part is a programme containing sets of commands programmed into the memory location of the Arduino microcontroller. A microcontroller is a device that cannot act on its own; it is a device that can be tailored to perform a specific function (Adelakun & Omolola, 2023). A program written in assembly language controls the microcontroller's response to the signal from the source of supply. The program was written to connect the sources of supply, the microcontroller, and the input and output components. The hardware part of the design involves the circuitry design, which includes the power supply circuit, the user interface, input modules, output modules, and the microcontroller, all connected on a Veroboard through soldering. The power supply circuit consists of an AC-DC power supply module that converts the alternating input voltage to a DC voltage of 12V. A voltage regulator module (LM7805) is then used to step down the 12VDC to a stable 5VDC, suitable for the microcontroller. Coupled with this is a battery backup solution that provides 12VDC power when there is a loss of power from the main power supply. The battery solution consists of 3 cells rated 3.7VDC, 1800mAh connected in series. Connecting the cells in series gives a total voltage of 11.7VDC, which is suitable to power the system. The batteries connected in series are connected to a 3S Battery Management System (BMS) which serves as protection when charging the batteries with 12VDC from the AC-DC power supply module. The 12VDC output from the battery solution is then passed through a switch, which is used to power the system.

The user interface section makes it possible for the system to tell the user what to do and makes it possible for the user to modify the system parameters. This section consists of the Liquid Crystal Display (LCD), a 1602 LCD Green Module, and the keypad module that can be used to adjust parameters. Parameters that can be modified are changing the Personal Identification Number (PIN), enrolling in a new fingerprint, and deleting an enrolled fingerprint. The input modules section of the project refers to input devices that send signals to the microcontroller. They allow the user to send their desired input to the microcontroller. They consist of the fingerprint sensor module that sends finger minutiae to the controller in the form of an electrical signal. Also in this section is the keypad module that sends the PIN input and other keypad-based input to the microcontroller. Finally, the exit push button is placed behind the door to allow exit from the enclosed spaces. The output module section consists of the relay module and an actuator that drives the solenoid lock, which is the final control element. This section also contains a

buzzer that energises upon access verification. The various units that make up the fingerprint door unlock system are shown in Figure 1, with the process flowchart represented in Figure 2.

Figure 1: Block diagram of a fingerprint door unlock system

Figure 2: Process flowchart of the door access system

The major components used in the design are: AS608 Optical Fingerprint Sensor, Arduino MEGA microcontroller, 1602 (16x2) LCD, 4*5 Numeric keypad, Electromagnetic (solenoid) door lock, Power supply modules, Relays and pushbutton switch

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Upon the completion of the dual access door control system, it was put to the test, and the results of the test showed the system to be very effective and easy to use. The system was powered, and the master fingerprint was registered. The password was also registered, set, and saved. Various fingerprints were enrolled and used to test the system. Unregistered fingerprints were also tested on the system, which resulted in "INVALID." On the keypad, buttons "0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, & 9" are used to input the password, while "#" is used to clear any digit. "F1" is used to change the password, while "F2" is used to manage the fingerprint functions: enrollment of a new finger and deletion of a finger. The arrow keys are used to navigate through the system.

"Ent" is used to acknowledge an action, while "ESC" is used to cancel any operation and return the system to the initial display as shown in Plate 1. The system allows the user to either use the password or a registered fingerprint to open the door. Access is granted when the correct password is supplied or when the fingerprint matches a pre-enrolled finger. It denies access when these conditions are not true. The buzzer beeps twice when access is granted and beeps three times when access is denied. The exit button placed behind the door is used to unlock the door directly.

Plate 1 shows the initial display of the system when powered, where it allows the user to either use the password or finger to unlock the system. As the user inputs the password, it is represented with an "*" on the LCD, as shown in Plate 2. Access is granted with two beeps if the password supplied by the user is correct, as shown in Plate 3, and access is denied with three beeps when the wrong password is supplied, as shown in Plate 4. To use the fingerprint (the finger must have been pre-enrolled), the user places the registered finger on the fingerprint sensor and, as is granted, beeps, as shown in Plate 5, if it matches a pre-enrolled finger. It denies access if the fingerprint does not match a pre-enrolled finger with three beeps, as shown in Plate 6.

To change the password, the "F1" button is pressed once, which prompts the user for the current password (the default password is "2018"). If the correct password is supplied, it prompts the user to supply the new password and saves the new password. Note: The password has to be four digits. The system also allows the user to manage the fingerprint data. To access this function, the "F2" button is pressed once, and the system prompts the master finger to authorise the fingerprint management operation. The master finger is automatically the first finger enrolled on the system, denoted as Finger 1. In the situation where no finger has been enrolled, the password "2021" can be used to override the master finger for authorization. The arrow keys are used to move through the two options, and "Ent" is used to select the desired option. The two options are "Add a new finger" and "Delete an existing finger."

When adding a new finger, the user is expected to place the desired finger on the fingerprint sensor twice. If the fingerprints are well processed, they are saved with an ID. The ID runs from 1 to 4, the first user is given Finger 1, and so on. To delete an existing finger, simply select the "Delete an existing finger" option from the "F2" menu. The ID of the finger to be deleted is entered, and the system deletes the finger. The images below show various stages of the system.

Plate 1: Initial Display of the System when Powered

Plate 2: A user inputs the password

Plate 3: Access Granted when Password Matches

Plate 4: Access Denied when a wrong Password is used

Plate 5: Access Granted when Fingerprint matches enrolled finger

Plate 6: Access Denied when finger does not match an enrolled finger

Plate 7: Picture view of the project after completion

CONCLUSION

Smart technologies will not only improve the systems of managing facilities, they will also hold the key to a more sustainable approach to developing and maintaining building facilities and infrastructure, an approach needed for economic growth. The concept of this paper employs the technology of a fingerprint biometric coupled with a DNC system that can be deployed in a place that requires a secured access system. From personal applications in homes, halls, and offices in schools, government, and private buildings, to highly secured military facilities, a smart dual-access door system, as achieved by this paper, provides a highly secured access system that is easy and convenient to use, by employing an economical means of control, the Arduino MEGA microcontroller. A smart dual-access door system using Arduino MEGA will always be a good choice for anyone who needs a secured access control system.

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